

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL
EDUCATION AND TRAINING (TVET) PROGRAMMES FOR EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT
AND ECONOMIC PROSPERITY IN BENUE STATE**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17219026>

ABSTRACT

The synergy between technical vocational education and training (TVET) and artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly significant as AI technologies are striving to develop essential industry relevant skills needed by workforce in this digital era. Adopting AI in TVET programme offers the above potentials which will in turn advance educational development and hence economic stability. Two research questions guided this study on adoption of artificial Intelligence in Technical and Vocational Education and Training Programmes for Educational Development and Economic Stability in Benue State. The study adopted the descriptive research design with 57 respondents as the population and sample of the study. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data and the data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation. It was revealed from the study that AI tools are sparsely adopted and utilized in TVET programme in Benue State and that available AI tools in TVET programme in Benue State are not sufficient to support students learning and address their skill development. Engaging teachers in professional development on AI tools use; investing in digital infrastructure and ensuring reliable access to electricity and internet were suggested and also recommended as some of the appropriate strategies for enhancing use of AI tools in TVET programmes in Benue State.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, TVET Programme, Educational Development, Economic Prosperity

INTRODUCTION

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) is heralding a profound shift in higher education, redefining how students learn and how teachers teach and under which environment is learning instructions being carried out. From intelligent tutoring systems to AI-driven content creation tools, the higher education landscape is experiencing a technological evolution with far-reaching implications. Thus, many have embraced AI to enhance learning outcomes, streamline administrative processes and foster more personalized educational experiences (Zume, 2025; Ayala-Pazmino, 2023).

The rapid integration of AI in higher education is fueled by advances in machine learning and data analytics and its acceleration by the covid-19 pandemic as opined by Harry (2023) and Zume (2025), has prompted education stakeholders including TVET educators to reflect on its extent of integration and application in higher education in Nigeria and Benue State. Lecturers' perspectives in this discourse are critical as they are both facilitators of learning and guardians of academic

standards and outcomes. Artificial intelligence (AI) in itself has been described by Selwyn (2019) as the act of making machines and digital computer system capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence like learning, language translation, problem-solving, visual-perception and decision-making.

TVET has been noted for playing a great role in preparation of its graduates with skills and competences needed to meet the demands of the dynamics work world and as capable workforce in the digital era. TVET has been defined as all forms an aspect of education that are Technical and Vocational in nature, provided either in educational institutions or under their authority, by public authorities, the private sector or through other forms of organized education, formal or non-formal, aiming to ensure that all members of the community have access to lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2009). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) stated its objectives for TVET as to:

- provide trained manpower in applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional level.
- provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agriculture, industry, commerce and economic development.
- provide people who can apply scientific knowledge to the improvement and solution of environmental problems for the use and convenience of man.
- give training and impart the necessary skills leading to the production of craftsmen, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant.
- enable young men and women to have intelligent understanding of the increasing complexities and evolution of technology.
- give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies.

As the world of work is experiencing a dynamic transformation, orchestrated by digitalization and automation, Artificial Intelligence and Information Technology are setting the standards for essential skills needed by workers, with highlight on necessity for new digital skills.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As the world enters the industry 5.0 era characterized by rapid technological advancements, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) with its benefits, Nigeria including Benue State finds itself at a crossroads, while these emerging technologies holds immense potential to revolutionize education and address long standing challenges such as obsolete equipment and machines or lack of them in TVET institutions, unemployment, lack of required skills by TVET graduates and outdated curriculum and lack of standard learning environment, their adoption into the Nigerian educational system has been limited by resource constraints, lack of digital literacy and infrastructure and concerns over ethical implication (Yakubu, 2024). These listed challenges facing its adoption in Nigeria TVET institutions, has led to a widening gap between the skills taught in schools and the skills required by employers in the AI-driven industry and economy. If this gap persist, Nigerian youths may be facing difficulties in getting jobs in the AI-powered industry. Hence, the solution lies on adopting AI into TVET to ensure that students are equipped and stand on high skill point on global scale.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. To what extent are AI tools currently being adopted into TVET institution programme in Benue State to enhance students' skill development?

2. What are the appropriate strategies for enhancing the use of AI tools in TVET programme in Benue State to improve students' skill development?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The synergy between Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and AI is increasingly significant as AI technologies reshape industries and labour markets in so many ways such as enhancing skill development through Adaptive Learning and Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS); industry-relevant training by using AI-driven models to predict industry skill demand, workforce readiness, education and employment and enterprise collaboration (Ukala & Iheukwumere, 2025).

To Omeh, Olelewe and Hu (2024), Nigeria Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and AI can enhance learning through personalize learning experience, Automate Administrative tasks and improve teaching quality by providing real-time feedback and data-driven insights, ultimately preparing students for the digital economy. Chu, et al. (2023) highlighted that AI provides TVET with opportunities such as tailored educational content as AI can be used to create customized educational content to cater for individual learner's need. It can facilitate interactive and immersive learning experience using synthetic humans, virtual replica of machinery, tools or even historical figures relevant to a particular trade, providing personalized feedback and learning pathways. McLaren (2024) also pointed out the AI can provide students with real-time feedback, simulating complex business scenarios and offering a level of interactivity that traditional educational methods cannot match.

Furthermore, personalized learning, improved engagement, enhanced assessment, increased access to education and improved teacher training are some of the impacts of AI on TVET according to Ndom-Uchendu & Nwokike (2024). Olumuyiusa & Ayodele (2023) noted that understanding how to leverage AI in business processes gives students a competitive edge in entrepreneurship, enabling them to innovate and lead their ventures. Also, that AI powered plat forms can facilitate collaboration among students by matching them with peers who have complementary skills or interests.

Harry (2023) and Adedoyin & Soykan (2020) also noted that one of the most prominent benefits of AI for student learning is personalization as the needs of every student is met through adaptive learning where students receive the support they need when they need it, especially for a slow-learner. Pendy (2023) agrees with Harry (2023) as he stated that AI-driven platforms are accessible anytime, anywhere, enabling students to learn at their own pace. With assessment students receive timely actionable feedback allowing them to adjust their learning strategies on time hence promoting efficiency in learning process (Kizilcec, 2017). Adedoyin and Oyeniran (2022) stressed that gamification, simulation and virtual reality (VR) keep students engaged and motivated therefore making abstract concepts tangible (Zume, 2025).

In addition, despite the numerous advantages and opportunities inherent in adopting AI in TVET in Nigeria, Uduafemhe (2021) identified lack of funding of TVET institutions, as the major challenges faced in the integration of AI in TVET in Nigeria states entirely. To Shuaibu (2024), infrastructural deficiency, financial resources, shortage of qualified trainers and AI experts, and ethical issues challenges AI adoption in Africa. Ethical issues, data privacy, authenticity and over dependence of students on AI against critical thinking, lack of access to necessary technology and infrastructure, lack of basic digital skills by teachers and students were all highlighted by Uzo (2021); Ogunbiyi (2019); Uteh and Iheukwumere (2024); Adeboye (2023); and Adefolalu and Okebukola (2020) as challenges of adopting AI in education system (TVET inclusive) in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was used for the study (Creswell & Hirose, 2019). The study was conducted in Benue State which comprise academic staff in 3 selected TVET public institutions from the three senatorial zones in the state. The population of the study is 57 respondents consisting of 33 academic staff from faculty of technology and industrial studies, Benue State University Makurdi; 12 academic staff from school of Vocational and Technical Education, College of Education Katsina-Ala and 12 academic staff from Benue State Polytechnic Ugbokolo. The researcher used all the population of the study since it is manageable and serve as a representative sample, hence no sampling was required.

The instrument for data collection for this study was a 19-item structured questionnaire to answer research question 1 and 2. The respondents were requested to rate the items on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree = 4, (3.5-4.0); Agree 3 = (2.5 – 3.49); Disagree 2 = (1.5 – 2.49) and Strongly Disagree 1 = (1.0 – 1.49). The instrument was validated by three experts and was subjected to internal consistency testing using Cronbach Alpha which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82 for the questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze data collected from the study. Any item whose mean value ranges from 2.50 above is accepted as valid but item whose mean value falls below the cut-off value of 2.50 is rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent are AI tools currently being adopted into TVET institution programme in Benue State to enhance students’ skill development?

Table 1: Mean ratings of respondents on the extent of adoption of AI tools in TVET programme in Benue State to enhance student skill development.

S/No		Mean	SD	Remark
1.	AI tools are effectively integrated to a high extent into the TVET curriculum to address the specific skill needs of students	2.16	0.58	Disagree
2.	The availability of AI tools in Nigeria TVET programme is sufficient to effectively support students’ learning and skill development to a high extent.	1.36	0.62	Strongly Disagree
3.	AI tools in TVET programmes will adequately prepare students for industry-relevant skills to a high extent.	3.81	0.53	Strongly Agree
4.	Students in TVET programme benefit to a high extent from AI tools that offer personalized learning experience tailored to their skills needs.	2.39	1.42	Disagree
5.	Students in TVET programmes are taught using audio-visual materials to a high extent in TVET institutions to enhance their practical skills	2.09	1.21	Disagree
6.	Most of the classrooms and workshops in Technical Colleges in Benue State have functional internet source to a high extent.	2.43	0.79	Disagree
7.	AI tools in TVET programmes will have significant improvement on students’ technical skills to a high extent.	3.76	0.50	Strongly agree
8.	AI tools are rarely being used to an extent to teach TVET students due to inadequate infrastructure.	3.54	0.68	Strongly Agree
		2.69	0.79	

The results on Table 1 revealed that items 1,2,4,5,6 was rejected by the respondents as their mean values fall below the cut off value of 2.50. However, items 3, 7 and 8 were accepted by the respondents as their mean values are 3.81, 3.76 and 3.54 respectively. Meanwhile, the cluster mean and standard deviation had a score of 2.69 and 0.79 respectively, thus affirming that AI tools are sparsely adopted into TVET programmes in Benue State.

Research Question 2: What are the appropriate strategies for enhancing use of AI tools in TVET programme in Benue State to improve students’ skill development?

Table 2: Mean ratings of respondents on the appropriate strategies for enhancing use of AI tools in TVET programme in Benue State to improve students’ skill development.

S/No		Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Use AI as a learning aid not a substitute	3.76	0.52	Strongly Agree
2.	Develop AI literacy for students to use	3.62	0.67	Strongly Agree
3.	Foster Ethical Decision-making	3.73	0.57	Strongly Agree
4.	Limit students over-reliance on AI	3.72	0.50	Strongly Agree
5.	Ensure students Acknowledge AI assistance	3.55	0.60	Strongly Agree
6.	Lecturers should clarify expectations on AI use	3.37	0.72	Agree
7.	Lecturers should model responsible AI use	2.65	0.65	Agree
8.	Redesign assignments to minimize AI misuse	3.68	0.67	Strongly Agree
9.	Use AI detection tools judiciously	3.76	0.45	Strongly Agree
10.	Engage in continuous professional development	3.81	0.53	Strongly Agree
11.	Integrate ethical AI use into the curriculum	3.65	0.79	Strongly Agree

Table 2 analysis indicated that all the items were accepted as the appropriate strategies of enhancing the use of AI tools in TVET programmes in Benue State for students’ skill development. The standard deviation values of the items ranged 0.45 – 0.79 which suggest that the responses of the respondents are close to each other.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question One sought the extent of adoption of AI tools in TVET institutions programme in Benue State to enhance students’ skill development. It was revealed that AI tools are sparsely adopted and utilized in TVET programmes in Benue State and that availability of AI tools in TVET programmes in institutions are not sufficient to effectively support students learning and address their needs for skill development. This is in line with the submission of Ogunbiyi (2019) that lack of access to necessary technology and infrastructure hinders the integration of AI in educational programmes in Nigeria.

Research Question Two investigated the appropriate strategies for enhancing use of AI in Benue State to improve students learning and skill development. The findings revealed some of the strategies appropriate for enhancing use of AI tools in TVET programmes to include: use of AI as a learning tools not a substitute for learning; teachers to engage in continuous professional development; development of AI literacy for students use; minimize or limit students’ over-reliance on AI; Redesign assignments to minimize AI misuse; lecturers should model responsible AI use amongst others. This finding agrees with Uteh and Iheukwumere (2024) and Adeboye (2023) who stated that over reliance of students on AI could undermine the development of critical thinking and creativity and also problem-solving skills which are essential to

entrepreneurship. Also Yakubu (2024) recommended that moving forward with integration of AI powered educational system will require investment in digital infrastructure and ensuring reliable access to electricity. Similarly, government establishing robust teacher training and professional development programme that focus on building competences in using AI tools and leveraging data-driven insights for personalized instructions was also recommended by Yakubu (2024).

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that Adopting AI with TVET programmes in institutions in Benue State will help in bridging skills gaps for workforce in this digital era as TVET play a pivotal role in equipping it's recipients with the necessary skills, knowledge and attitudes to meet the demands of AI driven world of work, subsequently eradicate unemployment, economic instability and achieve the objectives of TVET programme as enshrined in the Nigeria National Policy on Education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study therefore recommends that adopting AI in TVET programmes in Benue State is dependent on availability of resources which the government is encouraged to look into.
2. Government should establish a robust Teacher Training and Professional Development Programme for TVET teachers to upskill their digital literacy and competences in using AI tools.
3. Government should also invest in digital infrastructure and ensure availability of internet and electricity for effectiveness of AI powered tools and infrastructures.

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